

ASPECTS AND FORMATION OF SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ANNOTATION: The article is devoted to the influence of sociolinguistics on the process of teaching a foreign language. This work describes how important it is to take into account social and cultural factors in language teaching; it is necessary to take into account the social background of the country of the language being studied, integrating the social context and corresponding situations into teaching.

Key words: connection, sociolinguistics, teaching foreign language, social context, competence, linguistic, communication, students.

Sociolinguistics is the study of the connections between language and society. The essence of sociolinguistics is the study of the influence of social factors on the structure and use of language.

Sociolinguistic competence is as a component of communicative competence, reflecting the social orientation of learning, is “possession of a set of linguistic means and the ability to make their choice depending on the socio-cultural and situational aspects context” [4]. Sociolinguistic competence is the ability of an individual to select linguistic means adequately to the conditions of a communicative act.

Sociolinguistic competence is closely related to sociocultural competence, which presupposes the speaker’s knowledge of the sociocultural rules of language and speech. However, unlike sociocultural competence, it is aimed at studying and mastering the peculiarities of using certain linguistic means depending on the social situation, communicative tasks, topics, place of communication, social roles of the communicants, while sociocultural competence involves the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of speakers to correctly use the national and cultural characteristics of the social and speech behavior of native speakers [8].

The constituent components of sociolinguistic competence are various linguistic markers of social relations, which serve to express social status, socio-psychological distance and inequality in the status of participants in communication and are manifested in such linguistic units as vocabulary with a national-cultural component, phraseological units with national-cultural semantics, formulas of speech communication, proverbs, sayings, words, etc. [4].

The importance of social and cultural factors in language teaching cannot be overemphasized in sociolinguistics. Sociolinguistics places special emphasis on the use of language, highlights communication skills, views the study of language in relation to society and culture, since each language is a reflection of a particular culture and has deep cultural connotations.

If we are to fully master a language, we must have adequate knowledge of the rich social and cultural contexts in which the language exists. It will also benefit the understanding and use of language, as language and culture complement each other. Thus, introducing social and cultural knowledge into English language teaching is essential [10]. As an emerging discipline, sociolinguistics has not been around for very long, but it has had a great influence on the content and methods of teaching English language.

Speech behavior is formed differently depending on the given or existing situational situation or communicative context: the participants in communication, the conditions of its occurrence and the means of the communicative act. Each sphere and situation of communication requires the actualization of a certain set of components of sociolinguistic competence [14]. At the same time, role relationships, social status and socio-psychological distance between students of communication acquire special significance.

Thus, the speech behavior of communication participants is predetermined by the influence of various social factors, which involve the choice of certain verbal and non-verbal means of expressing communication (speech etiquette, intonation parameters of speech, socially marked vocabulary, etc. discourse markers) and in a certain social context form a speech portrait representatives.

To develop sociolinguistic competence, three technological components are required:

① Information and resource component, based on authentic didactic materials, selected on the basis of their functionality (correspondence to the topic of the lesson, relevance and novelty of information, compliance with the interests of students), situationality and problematic nature. The key point in the information and resource component of the technology for the formation of sociolinguistic competence of students is the didactic potential authentic materials [6]. Thus, the authenticity of multimedia and printed didactic tools contributes to the accumulation of knowledge about social values in a foreign language environment and the development of skills in comparing the social and cultural realities of a foreign language society with the realities of their native country, brings students closer to the real conditions of functioning of the language being studied, and creates cognitive interest in the regional and sociocultural aspects of the language.

② The interactive component of the technology for developing the sociolinguistic competence of future translators includes an algorithm for working with authentic material, which includes a choice of methodological techniques and forms that provide for a “communicative orientation, interactivity, reliance on interdisciplinary connections, development of the individual’s ability to self-organize, self-training and self-development” [2]. The algorithm for working with authentic material in the formation of sociolinguistic competence of students is constructed as follows:

- Introductory stage. At this stage, students become acquainted with new socially marked linguistic means and carry out their initial processing;
- Training stage. Students observe the peculiarities of the use of socially marked linguistic means in audiovisual material;
- Creative stage. The audiovisual material in students’ speech is being updated [2].

The effectiveness of the formation of sociolinguistic competence is ensured by a combination of classroom, extracurricular and independent controlled work of students.

③ The diagnostic component of the technology for developing sociolinguistic competence of students is represented by test, interactive and reflective diagnostic material.

Therefore, the model for the formation of sociolinguistic competence of students is a combination of target, content, technological and evaluation-effective blocks.

The maturity of students' sociolinguistic competence when mastering a foreign language is determined according to the criteria of the main four components of the competence being studied:

- linguopragmatic: the ability to organize speech interaction, understanding your partner's speech in a foreign language, the ability to regulate one's own communicative behavior and the behavior of partners;
- linguistic: knowledge of the stylistic and structural features of the text, mastery of speech etiquette formulas used in a particular social and communicative context [13];
- situational (extralinguistic): the ability to construct a statement in accordance with the communicative situation, the ability to determine missing information taking into account communication situation, the ability to respond adequately to a communicative situation;
- social-status: mastery of socially correct methods of addressing a partner, the ability to plan speech behavior taking into account one's social role and the role of a partner, the ability to build communication taking into account the characteristics of the partner's speech [3].

To determine the level of development of sociolinguistic competence of future specialists, the following criteria and indicators are identified:

❖ The motivational criterion for determining the level of development of students' sociolinguistic competence indicates that they have developed a positive attitude towards the foreign language they are learning, the formation of sociolinguistic competence, the development of personal qualities of a future specialist, tolerant communication and interaction with representatives of different ethnic groups, mastering professional knowledge, skills and abilities [5].

❖ The cognitive criterion for determining the level of development of students' sociolinguistic competence includes knowledge acquired in the process of studying a foreign language, skills and abilities.

❖ The communicative criterion for determining the level of development of students' sociolinguistic competence characterizes the students' communicative abilities of understanding and perceiving other people, the ability to correctly resolve conflict situations, and knowledge of ethics business communication.

The personal criterion for determining the level of development of students' sociolinguistic competence includes the professional and moral qualities of the individual, in demand for communication and interaction with representatives of different cultures in the process of professional activity [9].

The criteria for assessing the formation of the above skills in students' oral speech, according to N.A.Belenyuk are:

1. The ability to navigate a communication situation (tone of communication, method of communication, place of communication, communicative purpose and intention).
2. Correspondence of students' speech behavior to the model of speech behavior of native speakers in a similar situation.
3. Correct determination of communication goals and intentions of communication partners.

4. The correctness of determining the appropriateness of speech communication formulas when implementing a certain communicative intention and achieving a goal in the communication process.

5. The appropriateness of using speech communication formulas that implement certain communicative intentions, which will be determined by the compliance of the lexical and grammatical means used with the situational norm and national-cultural context [1].

Determining the level of development of students' sociolinguistic competence can be carried out according to five criteria on a low-medium-high scale:

- ☛ the ability to establish, in the process of communication, a respectful attitude towards the social values of native speakers of a foreign language;
- ☛ the ability to correctly interpret their sociocultural reality [11];
- ☛ the ability to make an appropriate choice of linguistic means in a given situation;
- ☛ the ability to choose a behavior strategy appropriate to the situation;
- ☛ the ability of self-control and self-education in order to increase the level of competence [2].

To sum up, the degree of formation of students' sociolinguistic competence when teaching foreign languages depends on the depth of their mastery of sociolinguistic knowledge in the aspect of social differentiation of speech at the level of pronunciation, vocabulary and phraseological units with a national cultural component, formulas of speech communication, proverbs as well as the ability to analyze speech in order to recognize the speech characteristics of representatives of different social strata and select a model of the speech situation that is adequate to the given situation [15].

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